

Lane: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15

Primer set
A6

Primer set
B103

Well samples from left to right. Top row identical to bottom row with the exception of the primer:
Patient 1 non-tumour, Patient 1 tumour, Patient 2 non-tumour, Patient 2 tumour, Patient 3 non-tumour, Patient 3 tumour, Patient 4 non-tumour, Patient 4 tumour, Patient 5 non-tumour, Patient 5 tumour, Patient 5 regrowth tumour, Patient 6 non-tumour, Patient 6 tumour, Empty well, Negative template control.

Lane: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15

Primer set
C102

Primer set
D108

Well samples from left to right. Top row identical to bottom row with the exception of the primer:
Patient 1 non-tumour, Patient 1 tumour, Patient 2 non-tumour, Patient 2 tumour, Patient 3 non-tumour, Patient 3 tumour, Patient 4 non-tumour, Patient 4 tumour, Patient 5 non-tumour, Patient 5 tumour, Patient 5 regrowth tumour, Patient 6 non-tumour, Patient 6 tumour, Empty well, Negative template control.

Lane: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15

PCR not associated with this study

Primer set B123

Well samples from left to right, bottom row. Top row not used in study: DNA ladder, Negative template control, Patient 1 non-tumour, Patient 1 tumour, Patient 2 non-tumour, Patient 2 tumour, Patient 3 non-tumour, Patient 3 tumour, Patient 4 non-tumour, Patient 4 tumour, Patient 5 non-tumour, Patient 5 tumour, Patient 5 regrowth tumour, Patient 6 non-tumour, Patient 6 tumour.